

Copper(II) Complexes containing Mixed Ligands

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Mixed ligand complexes of copper(II), $\text{Cu(L)}_4\text{-(ReO}_4)_2$, where L = pyridine, NH_3 , have been reported¹. We considered the possibility of formation of analogous compounds with metavanadate ion VO_3^- in place of the perrhenate, especially in view of the fact that metavanadate ion is not yet known to exist as a discrete unit in the solid state². The complex prepared, however, turned out to contain H_2VO_4^- rather than VO_3^- , having composition $\text{Cu}_2(\text{py})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_4$ and $\text{Cu}_4(\text{bpy})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_8$. Attempts to synthesise the corresponding compound containing ammonia did not succeed.

Results and Discussion

The compounds (Table 1) are insoluble in water and common organic solvents although they appear to be partly dispersed in some of them. The molar conductance data ($1.0\text{--}2.0 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ in DMF, 10^{-5}M) indicate their non-electrolytic nature. Thermogravimetric analysis of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{py})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_4$, recorded upto 700° , shows a weight-loss of 19.4% at $320\text{--}340^\circ$ corresponding to loss of two molecules of pyridine (calcd. 18.98%). The TG curve of $\text{Cu}_4(\text{bpy})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_8$ recorded upto 800° , shows the decomposition at 780° having 28.3% weight-loss corresponding to loss of three molecules of 2,2'-bipyridyl (calcd. 28.2%).

The reflectance spectrum of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{py})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_4$ exhibits a broad band at 680 nm, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{bpy})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_4$ shows bands at 660 nm and 860 nm w. A square-planer configuration for copper(II) is thus indicated for both the complexes⁴. Ir spectra of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{py})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_4$ and $\text{Cu}_4(\text{bpy})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_8$ show bands (Table 1) due to coordinated pyridine and 2,2'-bipyridyl molecules^{5,6}. The pyridine bands cor-

respond to polymeric octahedral copper(II) structure⁶. However, a clearcut picture of copper(II) configuration does not appear to emerge from the spectral data. The V-O stretch and VOH bending modes indicate the involvement of H_2VO_4^- ions as bridging groups.

Experimental

The chemicals were used of A.R. grade. Cu was estimated iodometrically³ and V spectrophotometrically³ using a Systronics 105 MKI spectrophotometer. Conductance was measured with a Systronics 303 conductivity meter. Estimation of nitrogen and recording of ir spectra were carried out at the Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur. TG analysis and reflectance spectra were obtained from Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab.

$\text{Cu}_2(\text{py})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_4$: To copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate (1 g, 0.004 mol) dissolved in a minimum volume of water, pyridine (1.25 ml, 0.015 mol) was added and to the resulting blue solution hot ($70\text{--}80^\circ$) aqueous solution of ammonium monovanadate (0.9 g, 0.004 mol) was added with stirring. The green precipitate formed was allowed to settle for 30 min, washed with water containing 1% pyridine and with 50% alcohol and then dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 .

$\text{Cu}_4(\text{bpy})_3(\text{H}_2\text{VO}_4)_8$: To copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate (0.5 g, 0.002 mol) dissolved in a minimum volume of water was added 2,2'-bipyridyl (0.6 g) dissolved in a minimum volume of absolute alcohol. Then a hot ($70\text{--}80^\circ$) aqueous solution of ammonium mono-vanadate (0.5 g, 0.0022 mol) was added to it slowly with stirring. The initial blue precipitate

*Now deceased.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / Colour	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)			ν(OH)	VOH bend	ν ₁ (V O)	ν ₂ (V-O)	ν ₃ (V O)	Bands due to heterocyclic bases
	Cu	V	N						
Cu ₂ (py) ₃ (H ₂ VO ₄) ₄ (Green)	15.15 (15.28)	24.16 (24.50)	4.97 (5.05)	3440	1065	820	753	328	445, 649
Cu ₄ (bpy) ₃ (H ₂ VO ₄) ₈ (Bright green)	14.88 (15.33)	24.43 (24.59)	5.57 (5.07)	3480	1172	780	745	314	416, 745, 1019, 1443

changed to bright green colour. It was allowed to stand for ca 30 min, washed with distilled water and with 50% alcohol and dried over concentrated H₂SO₄.

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